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Short Synthesis of (Z)-7-Heneicosene and (Z)-7-Tricosene

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RECENTLY it has been found that (Z)-7-heneicosene (1) and (Z)-7-tricosene (2) are the pheromone components of *A. eurtula*^{1,2}. The strategy for the construction of 1 and 2 is depicted in Scheme 1. The reaction sequence involves the preparation of 4-undecyn-1-ol (3) by reacting tetra-

hydrofurfuryl chloride with n-hexyl bromide in presence of lithium amide in liquid ammonia³. Partial hydrogenation of acetylenic bond in 3 using Lindlar's catalyst in presence of quinoline yielded (Z)-4-undecene (4) in 90% yield. Bromination of 4 with PBr₃/Py in anhydrous ether gave 1-bromo-(Z)-4-undecene (5) the Grignard of which was then coupled⁴ with decyl bromide and dodecyl bromide in presence of catalytic amount of Li₂CuCl₄ at -10° in anhydrous THF as solvent. The purification of the coupled product using silica gel (200-100 mesh; Acme) afforded (Z)-7-heneicosene (1) and (Z)-7-tricosene (2) respectively in 60% yield.

Experimental

The compounds were purified by column chromatography using silica gel (200-100 mesh; Acme) and thin layer chromatography using silica gel G (NCL, Poona). The purity was confirmed by elemental analysis from Regional Sophisticated Instrumentation Centre, Panjab University, Chandigarh. Ir spectra were recorded on Perkin-Elmer 337 spectrophotometer and ¹H nmr spectra on a Varian EM-390 (90 MHz) spectrophotometer using tetramethylsilane as an internal reference. The organic extracts were dried over Na₂SO₄. The air and moisture sensitive reactions were carried out under N₂ atmosphere.

4-Undecyn-1-ol (3): Tetrahydrofurfuryl chloride (12.0 g, 0.1 mol) was added to a stirred solution of lithium amide (0.3 mol; prepared from 2.1 g Li metal) in liquid ammonia during 15 min. After 3 h stirring, 1-bromohexane (16.5 g, 0.1 mol) dissolved in dry THF was added during 30 min. The reaction mixture was then quenched with saturated solution of NH₄Cl after 3 h stirring and the residue extracted in ether. The solvent was evaporated and subsequent column chromatography afforded 3 (10.08 g, 60%) (Found: C, 78.42; H, 11.78. C₁₁H₂₀O requires: C, 78.57; H, 11.90%); $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 3 600-3 500 (OH) and 2 210 cm⁻¹ (acetylenic); δ (CCl₄) 3.6 (3H, m, CH₂OH), 2.1

(4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.29 (10H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.85 (3H, t, CH₃).

(Z)-4-Undecenol (4): The alcohol (3; 8.4 g, 0.05 mol) was shaken with H₂-gas under pressure in presence of Lindlar's catalyst and a few drops of quinoline in dry n-hexane. When one equivalent of H₂ was absorbed, the hexane extract was washed with water and dried. Subsequent column chromatography afforded (Z)-4-undecenol (4; 7.65 g, 90%) (Found: C, 77.59; H, 12.85. C₁₁H₂₂O requires: C, 77.64; H, 12.94%); $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 3 500–3 300 (OH), 2 900, 1 650, 1 470 and 720 cm⁻¹ (cis-double bond); δ (CCl₄) 5.4–5.6 (2H, m, olefinic), 3.6 (3H, m, CH₂OH), 2.1–2.2 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.5–1.6 (10H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.9 (3H, t, CH₃).

(Z)-4-Undecenyl bromide (5): To the ice-cooled mixture of the alcohol (4; 2 g, 0.01 mol), pyridine (1 ml) and dry ether (100 ml) was added dropwise PBr₃ (0.56 ml, 0.005 mol) with stirring and the mixture refluxed for 2 h. A little amount of cold water was then added to it followed by saturated solution of NaHCO₃ till effervescence ceased. The ether extract was dried and evaporated to get 5 (2.19 g, 80%). The absence of ir band at 3 500–3 300 cm⁻¹ (OH) confirmed the formation of the bromide (5). It was used as such for next operation.

(Z)-7-Henicosene (1): A mixture of Mg metal (2.24 g, 0.01 mol) in dry THF (10 ml) was stirred under N₂-atm. The reaction was initiated by the addition of a little amount of 1,2-dibromoethane and then the bromide (5; 2.33 g, 0.01 mol) in THF (10 ml) was added. The Grignard so prepared was brought to the temperature -10° and decyl bromide (2.21 g, 0.01 mol) in THF (10 ml) was added dropwise. After 1 h stirring, catalytic amount of Li₂CuCl₄ was added and the temperature (-10°) maintained for further 3 h. The reaction mixture was then quenched with saturated solution of NH₄Cl and extracted with ether. The ethereal layer was dried and evaporated. Subsequent column chromatography using petroleum ether-ether (9:1) as eluent yielded 1 (1.75 g, 60%) (Found: C, 85.67; H, 14.32. C₃₂H₆₄ requires: C, 85.71; H, 14.28%); $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 2 900, 1 650, 1 470 and 725 cm⁻¹ (cis-double bond); δ (CCl₄) 5.4–5.6 (2H, m, olefinic), 2.1–2.2 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.4–1.6 (30H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.8–0.9 (6H, m, terminal 2 × CH₃).

(Z)-7-Tricosene (2): It was prepared according to the procedure described for 1 (Found: C, 85.61; H, 14.38. C₂₈H₅₆ requires: C, 85.71; H, 14.28%); $\nu_{\max}$ (neat) 2 950, 1 660, 1 470 and 720 cm⁻¹ (cis-double bond); δ (CCl₄) 5.4–5.5 (2H, m, olefinic), 2.0–2.2 (4H, m, allylic CH₂), 1.3–1.6 (34H, m, saturated CH₂) and 0.9 (6H, m, 2 × CH₃).

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Synthesis of some New (E)-1,2-Bis(alkylthio and alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes

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It is evident from literature that some studies have been made on the reaction¹⁻⁴ of aromatic thiols with benzoin. However no attempt has been made on the reactions between aliphatic thiols with benzoin. Aromatic thiols react with benzoin and gave *trans*-1,2-bis(arylthio)stilbenes¹⁻⁴ in poor yields. On the other hand, aliphatic thiols with benzoin gave (E)-1,2-bis(alkylthio)stilbenes (1a-f) in fair to good yields. Compounds 1a-f on oxidation with 30% hydrogen peroxide yielded (E)-1,2-bis(alkylsulphonyl)stilbenes (2a-f) (Scheme 1). The bis(organosulphonyl)ethylenes⁵⁻¹⁰ are well-known for their fungicidal activity. Since benzoin with aromatic thiols gives only *trans* isomers²⁻⁴, the compounds obtained in the present investigation should also possess *trans* (E)-configuration.

R = OH₂(CH₂)₂, (OH)₂OH, OH₂(CH₂)₃, (OH)₂OHCH₂, CH₂(OH)₂, and (OH)₂CH(OH)₂

Scheme 1

Experimental

All the melting points are uncorrected. The uv spectra (EtOH) were recorded on a Beckman DU-2 spectrophotometer and ir spectra (KBr) on a Perkin-Elmer 684 spectrophotometer.

(E)-1,2-Bis(alkylthio)stilbenes (1). (E)-1,2-Bis(n-propylthio)stilbene: To a solution of benzoin (5 g) in glacial acetic acid (65 ml), n-propanethiol was added and saturated with dry hydrogen chloride gas for 2.5 h. Powdered zinc chloride (10 g) was then added to it and hydrogen chloride was passed for 1 h. The reaction mixture was left in a refrigerator for one day. The resulting crystals were filtered, washed with cold ethanol followed by petroleum ether (b.p. 40–60°) and recrystallised from ethanol (4 g, 77%), m.p. 86° (Found: C, 73.08; H, 7.17. C₂₀H₂₄S₂ requires: C, 73.17; H, 7.32%).